

A Study of Lexical Errors on Student's Writing of 6th Semester English Education Students

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Abstract

Language writing errors are something that often happens. Especially for language learners. In Indonesia, English is a foreign language. This makes language learning feel a little difficult in writing. This research is an analysis of 6th semester English language education students at Muhammadiyah University, Tangerang. In this research, researchers used descriptive method and collecting the data by using in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. Moreover, the technique that researcher used is observation and documentation study related to writing in finding errors in writing made by students. Students often use online translation tools without double-checking the words. This leads to many lexical errors being generated by online translation tools. There were 15 students who were used as material for analysis this time. The results show that there are four out of seven types of lexical errors in students' writing. These are errors in choosing words, collocation errors, redundancy errors, and spelling errors.

Keywords: Lexical Errors; Semantic; Writing.

INTRODUCTION

Language skills play an important role in learning a language. Husain (2015) stated that a skill can be defined as the ability to perform something well. Understanding these concepts is a cognitive exercise, whereas applying them is a skill. Language is a complex talent with four sub-skills: listening, writing, reading, and speaking to effectively communicate with others, language learners must master all aspects of the language. In the early stages of language learning, students may understand basic grammar structures instinctively or through formal instruction, allowing them to form simple sentences and express basic ideas. On the other hand, learning a language can present several problems and difficulties, making the process more complex and sometimes frustrating, particularly for EFL students.

Ellis stated in Rattanadilok Na Phuket & Normah Othman (2015) when learning a new language, people often make connections between what they know and what they don't. Learners apply what they already know about their native language to their target language performances. Learning a new language without prior knowledge of its linguistic aspects is common. Richard in Najah & Agustina, (2020) language errors can occur when a second language learner's mother tongue is not the same as their first language. Mother tongue patterns can also have an impact on second language acquisition. This results in rejected measurement inaccuracies that create interference. Interference refers to problems made when speaking one language to another, including pronunciation, grammar, and vocabulary (Nurkholis, 2018).

However, according to Rao (2017) writing is a challenging skill for EFL/ESL learners to master, despite its importance in language development. The majority of students are at ease when they listen to others or read. Indrilla & Ciptaningrum (2018) , said that Expressing thoughts and emotions through written language is how individuals communicate. Visible indications, comprehensible not just to himself but to everyone else as well. It emphasizes that writing entails the formation of visual symbols or marks on a surface, whether it's paper, digital screens, or another medium. Therefore, the sixth semester of English Education students of University Muhammadiyah Tangerang has Paragraph Writing as one of the subjects. However, the student will not always use the correct English. They continue to struggle with writing in their daily tasks. They occasionally still utilize online dictionaries and translations as aids.

However, Semantic errors in writing refer to mistakes that occur when the meaning intended by the writer is not correctly conveyed to the reader. According to Özkayran & Yilmaz (2020), semantics

is the study of meaning, and any deviation from intended meaning in written text constitutes a semantic error. Furthermore, Lexical errors are mistakes related to the vocabulary of a language. These errors can be broadly defined as deviations from the standard usage of words, which result in incorrect or unclear expressions. Lexical errors can affect both spoken and written communication, leading to confusion or misinterpretation by the listener or reader. According to Anggreni & Bochari (2021) lexical errors are distinct from grammatical errors in that they pertain specifically to the incorrect selection or form of words rather than the structural arrangement of sentences. (Ander & Yildirim, 2010) also state that there is 7th types of lexical errors, such as Errors of Wrong word choice, Errors of Literal Translation, Errors of Omission or Incompletion, Errors of Redundancy, Misspelling, Errors of Collocation, and Errors of Word Formation.

Like in the previous study in Almahameed & Al-Shaikhli (2017) included 30 Jordanian English students who were assigned to write a composition of up to 150 words on a specific topic. The essays were then checked for grammatical and semantic problems. Participants in the study made various syntactic errors, such as errors in verb-tense, agreement, auxiliary usage, conjunctions, word order, resumptive pronouns, null-subjects, double-subjects, superlatives, comparatives, and possessive pronouns. Conversely, semantic errors were divided into errors occurring at the sentence level and those at the word level. Among the syntactic errors, the study found that verb-tense errors were the most prevalent, while comparative errors and errors in possessive pronouns were less common. Additionally, semantic errors at the word level were much more numerous than those at the sentence level.

Based on the explanation provided above, the researcher will look at grammatical errors in lexical semantics made by 6th semester English education students at Muhammadiyah University in Tangerang. The researcher is focusing on grammatical errors in lexical semantics. Lexical semantics deals with the meaning and interpretation of words, phrases, and sentences. The main goal of the research is to investigate these grammatical errors and identify the challenges faced by students. By understanding the specific errors and challenges, the aim is to help lecturers improve the quality of students' writing.

METHODOLOGY

According to Gay & Mills (2019) qualitative research involves gathering, collecting, and rendition extended narrative and audiovisual information to understand a specific phenomenon concern. In this research, researchers used descriptive qualitative, namely presenting the data as it is without manipulation or other treatment. The aim of this research is to present a complete picture of an event or is intended to explain and clarify a phenomenon that occurs (Rusandi & Muhammad Rusli, 2021). The qualitative data in this study focuses on examining how the Lexical Errors in student English writing in reference paper that student made.

It focuses to determine lexical grammatical errors made by 6th semester English language education students at Muhammadiyah University, Tangerang. Researchers used in-depth interviews and focus group discussions to gather detailed accounts of participants' experiences. Open-ended questions encourage participants to share their common grammatical error types are frequently used in their English writing. The technique that researcher used is observation and documentation study related to writing in finding errors in writing made by students.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In this study, the data from 15 writing samples produced by 6th-semester English language education students were analyzed. The researcher examined the students' foreword sections of their paper assignments. Each text was carefully reviewed, and lexical errors were identified and classified according to established categories. Moreover, From the analyzed data, a significant number of word choice errors, errors of redundancy, collocation errors, and misspelling were identified. Wrong word choice occurs when a word is used inappropriately due to phonetic similarity or identical spelling with a different meaning, whereas collocation errors result from the incorrect combination of words, leading to unnatural or incorrect expressions, errors of redundancy is category includes lexical errors that occur

when a word is used, repeated, or paraphrased excessively, then misspelling is Misspelling in lexical errors refers to mistakes related to the incorrect spelling of words. It occurs when a word is spelled incorrectly, either by omitting letters, adding extra letters, or using the wrong sequence of letters.

1. Errors of Wrong Word Choice

The data could be seen on the following table.

Table 1. Errors of Wrong Word Choice

No.	Students' Writing	Correction
1.	"The author realizes that in this writing there are still many shortcomings and mistake"	In this sentence, it should be "Acknowledging" because it more official and appropriate for writing, showing that the author recognizes and accepts the presence of flaws and errors. It is frequently employed in formal circumstances, making it better suited for written work instead of "realizes".
2.	"This paper is made with the best ability and knowledge that the author has."	In this sentence, it should be "Crafted" because this verb indicates a higher level of ability and care in the creative process. It indicates that the author put thought and effort into the work, making it appear more polished and sophisticated.
3.	"The author is fully aware that this paper is still far from perfect due to the limited experience and knowledge that the author has".	In this sentence, the "Fully aware" should be "Acknowledges" for more concise and direct. While the word "Limited" could be "Modest" expresses humility without being unduly critical or negative. It implies that, while the author realizes that their experience and understanding are limited, they are not completely lacking. Also using "Author" twice make a repetitive and less engaging, so the sentence should be " The author is acknowledging that this paper is still far from perfect given the modest experience and knowledges. "
4.	"The author would like to thank all those who have given the writer the enthusiasm and motivation in making this thesis work."	In this sentence, it's not a formal sentence. The word "enthusiasm" could be "encouragement" because it's fits better in the context. While the verb "in making" is less formal, it could be "during the creation of-". In the word "given" also should be "provide" and "thank all" should be "express gratitude". So, the sentence could be " The author would like to express gratitude to all those who have provide encouragement and motivation during the creation of this thesis ".
5.	"... and also, to my friends in arms who helped the writer in various ways."	In this sentence, the word "helped" is more formal if use "assisted". This suggests providing direct, practical assistance and support, which is fitting if your friends were actively involved in the completion of your thesis.
6.	"Although this proposal has many deficiencies in the arrangement and explanation."	The term "deficiencies" can be perceived as rather negative and harsh, as it strongly suggests significant faults or shortcomings. Conversely, the word "limitations" is softer and more neutral, acknowledging areas for improvement without implying severe faults.
7.	"The author is very useful ; I hope this paper is useful and can increase knowledge."	Describing a person as "useful" is perhaps the intention was to convey that the author is knowledgeable or capable. A more accurate and appropriate description of the author's expertise or capability would be "The author is very knowledgeable."
8.	"In completing this paper, the writer gets lots challengers."	"Get" is not used correctly in this context. "Get" is typically used to express receiving or obtaining something, but in this context, the intention is to meet or face challenges. It should be replaced with "encounters".
9.	"Writing this paper is a requirement to perform mid-term	"Perform" may not precisely denote the action associated with finalizing a paper. It implies a more active

test assignments."	implementation rather than completion. Moreover, "fulfill" aptly signifies meeting the requisites of the mid-term test assignments.
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2. The data of the errors of redundancy.

Table 2. Errors of Redundancy

No.	Students' Writing	Correction
1.	"The author is very useful . I hope this paper is useful and can increase knowledge"	The term "useful" is employed twice in close succession, resulting in a repetitive and less engaging sentence. Redundancy in writing can render the text unrefined and divert attention from the intended message.
2.	"Submitted as One of the Conditions Participating in the Mid Semester Examination for Academic Speaking Subject."	The phrase "Participating in the Mid Semester Examination" is redundant because "submitted as one of the conditions" already implies that the submission pertains to exam participation. The original phrase can be made more formal and concise by removing unnecessary words and restructuring it. The sentence should be, "Submitted as one of the conditions for the Mid Semester Examination in the Academic Speaking Subject."

3. The data of the Errors of Collocation

Table 3. Errors of Collocation

No.	Students' Writing	Correction
1.	" The author is very useful . I hope this paper is useful and can increase knowledge"	This phrase of "the author is very useful" is awkward because "useful" is not typically used to describe a person. Instead, it should be commonly describing individuals as "knowledgeable," "experienced," "skilled", or "helpful".
2.	"Author can complete this proposal as one of the requirements to carry out the midterm exam assignment"	The phrase "to carry out" is not typically used in the context of completing an assignment. "Carry out" often implies executing or performing a task or action. However, in the context of an academic assignment, the more appropriate collocation would be "to fulfill" or "to complete" the assignment.
3.	"There is a material discrepancy ."	"Material discrepancy" may not be the most fitting term for the context, particularly if the distinction being described isn't connected to physical materials. Furthermore, "significant difference" is a more adaptable and frequently utilized phrase that can depict variations in various contexts, rendering it more suitable for general use.

4. The data of Misspelling

Table 4. Misspelling

No.	Students' Writing	Correction
1.	"In completing this paper, the writer gets lots challengers ."	"Challengers" should be spelled as "challenges" to describe the challenges faced by the writer. This is a spelling error that affects the meaning of the word. "Challenges" means "tantangan" in English, while "challengers" does not exist in English and does not have a corresponding meaning.

CONCLUSION

Based on the discussion above, the researcher can conclude that there were lexical errors in writing forewords in papers written by 6th semester students. There are four types of seven types of lexical errors. Among them are errors in choosing words, redundancy errors, collocation errors, and spelling errors. This error was written by the student in the foreword of the paper. The papers created are part of the students' assignments during learning. Students often use online translations but do not

double-check the resulting words. As a result, there are lexical errors produced by online translation. This makes more considerations for other students if they want to use online translation, to check every word produced..

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